

Remaining Life Assessment of Refinery Furnace Tubes Using Finite Element Method

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ABSTRACT

Crude oil heater 9Cr-1Mo steel tubes from a refinery plant were studied, after 5 years of service at nominally 650 C° and 3 bar, to predict their remnant lives. The investigation included dimensional, hardness and tensile measurements in addition to accelerated stress rupture tests between 650 C° and 700 C° and microstructural examination. Tube specimens were taken from two sections, the overheated side and the side which only saw the nominal operating temperature. The method employed involved the prediction of the increase in temperature with increasing sediment deposition during the operating life times using an FEM model. In addition the predicted temperatures are used to derive appropriate creep properties at relevant temperatures in a 3D pipe FEM creep analysis to predict the pipe deformation rate. All compare well with the actual service exposed pipe measurements and layer deposition. The overheated side revealed a small loss of creep strength in a stress rupture test. A layer of sediment (appr. 10 mm thickness) consisting basically of sintered carbon (coke) spread over the inside of the tube was acting as a thermal barrier causing the temperature to rise above 650 C°. Analysis for the overheated side predicted an upper bound temperature of 800 C° and a life of about 50 h suggesting that failure by creep rupture could occur rapidly in the sediment region.

Keywords: Refinery Furnace Tube Design, Thermal Stress Test, Stress and Temperature Distribution, Finite Element Method, Solid Modeling, Failure Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Internally pressurized tubes are critical components in heat exchanger applications, such as boiler water tubes, steam super heater elements and chemical plant reformer tubes [1, 2]. Such tubes in power plants have a finite life because of prolonged exposure to high temperatures, stresses and aggressive environments.

Remaining life assessment of aged power plant components in the present highly competitive industrial scene has become necessary both for economic and safety reasons as most of the power plants are over 25 years old. In real life situations both premature retirement and life extension in relation to the original design life can be encountered [2].

The consequences of failure of a component in use can be tragic and expensive. There are many cases of engineering disasters resulting in loss of life and property. For boiler components, utmost attention is required to ensure that such incidents cannot take place. Carbon and 9Cr-1Mo steels are extensively used in high temperature components in power plants. Even though most of these components have a specific design life of 20 years, past experience has shown that they can have significant remaining life beyond the original design specification [3].

One of the most widely used techniques for life assessment of components involves removal of service exposed alloy and conducting accelerated tests at temperatures above the service temperature [4]. The aim of the present work is to evaluate the remaining life of Crude oil heater 9Cr-1Mo steel tubes from a refinery plant, after 5 years of service, based on experimental and numerical analysis.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The material specification with service condition and history of operation of the exposed 9Cr-1Mo steel super heater and re-heater tubes from a refinery furnace that heats crude oil at 350 C°, but outside tubes (convection zone and radiation zone) were around 650-690 C°.

So we have a furnace tube design, operating and safety information's are given in Table 1. Due to impurities in crude oil, basically sintered carbon (coke) has been deposited on the lower half of the tube section (Fig. 2.2). In this section, the rate of heat transfer from the tube to the crude oil would therefore decrease. In order to keep the temperature of the crude oil constant at 350 C° more heat is required and subsequently material at this section (Fig. 2.2) will experience a higher temperature in comparison to the other side.

This increase of temperature leads to higher physical and metallurgical damage, hence leading to a shorter safe operating time. In this article an experimental comparison has been made between the overheated and not-overheated side using manufacturing details and FEM results.

Table 1. Material Specification, Dimension and Condition of the Service Exposed Tubes (9Cr-1Mo Steel)

Material Specification/Grade of Steel	(ASTM) A220-T9
Design oil pressure (bar)	6
Operating steam pressure (bar)	4
Design inner surface temperature(C)	420
Operating inner surface temperature (C)	400
Operating outer surface temperature (C)	690
Tube thickness (mm)	6.35
Inner diameter (mm)	168
Service exposed (h)	43200

Fig.2.1 One Stack Box Type - Refinery Furnace

Fig.2.2 Higher Temperature Cause Sintered Coke Usually at the Bottom of Tubes in Convection Zone, and when the Temperature Distribution Comparison to the Other Side.

3. THERMAL ANALYSIS

The FEA Command CONV is applied on inner side of the model CONV are applied on outer side of the model. Solid 87 3-D 10-Node tetrahedral thermal solid (fig.3.1) is well suited to model irregular meshes.

The element has one degree of freedom, temperature, at each node. The boundary conditions presented in Fig.3.1. And maximum induced thermal stresses are presented in Fig.3.2 & Fig.3.3. As such under the actual operating conditions the component would be safe. The maximum temperature redeveloped is 400°C which is less than the recommended operating of (ASTM) A200-V01.

Fig.3.1.The Boundary Conditions

Fig.3.2.Maximum Induced Stresses

Fig.3.3.Detailed View of Maximum Induced Stresses

4. CONCLUSIONS

Crude oil heater 9Cr-1Mo steel tubes from a refinery plant after 5 year of service at nominally 650°C and 3 bar were studied to predict their remnant life. A software program using accelerated creep testing and metallographic investigation in parallel with a numerical analysis was used to perform the remnant life calculation of the service aged tubes. The method employed involved the prediction of the increase in temperature with increasing sediment deposition during the operating life times. In addition the predicted temperatures were used to derive appropriate creep properties at relevant temperatures in a 3D pipe FEM creep analysis to predict the pipe bending deformation rate. These compare well with the actual service exposed pipe measurements and conditions. All results indicate that in the overheated side of the tube, the creep life was reduced substantially but on the side under normal operating temperature significant remnant life still exists. It is also shown that the growth of sediment thickness is approximately proportional to the rise in temperature and pipe deformation (pipe bend).

The stresses induced in the tubes as shows in fig.3.3 and fig.3.2 are complex and ANSYS macro can handle this kind of complex shapes easily. The stress levels are within acceptable limit as per ASTM, A200-V01. As such under the actual operating conditions the component would be safe The maximum temperature redeveloped is 400°C which is less than the recommended operating 9Cr-1Mo Material.

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